

1 **Thioredoxin reductase modulation in human neurodegenerative disease.**

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6 A neurodegenerative disease has been described in the Pacific Islands known as Kii ALS/PDC (the
7 amyotrophic lateral sclerosis/parkinsonism-dementia complex) in which the pathologic features of ALS, PD
8 and AD can be found: protein aggregates in the brain of TDP-43, alpha-synuclein, and tau. Using induced
9 pluripotent stem cells from patients with Kii ALS/PDC we recently described transcriptional activation of an
10 enzyme, COMT, that was a shared transcriptional feature of the gene expression signature in induced
11 pluripotent stem cells from humans with Parkinson's Disease, ALS, and to lesser extent but still
12 significantly, in Alzheimer's Disease. The data alluded to an underlying metabolic deficiency that supported
13 neurotoxicity, and demonstrated this was a shared feature of neurodegenerative disease in humans. We
14 report here the discovery of a second shared metabolic or biochemical vulnerability in human
15 neurodegenerative disease, the induction of thioredoxin reductase *TXNRD2*. *TXNRD2* induction could be
16 found in neural stem cells that model the LRRK2 G2019S mutation found in humans with Parkinson's
17 Disease, and in motor neurons from humans with amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS). Less quantitatively
18 significant but still remarkable was increased expression of *TXNRD2* in Alzheimer's Disease iPS-derived
19 microglia with engineered APOE4 mutation. Importantly, *TXNRD2* was the single most closely
20 transcriptionally co-regulated gene across the entire transcriptome, with COMT. Neurodegenerative
21 disease in humans is defined by *TXNRD2* and *COMT* expression.
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